

QUIZ

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 7

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. which of the following is true about research questions or research objectives?**
 - Research questions are developed at beginning of a project but in qualitative research, they can be formulated and modified later in the process.¹**
 - Research question is the major intent of the study which enables the reader to understand the central thrust of the research.
 - Research questions refers to how you will go about addressing the problem.
 - Qualitative research objective usually starts with "how"" or "in what ways" and "what."
- 2. Which of the following is not a true about "trustworthiness" in research?**

¹ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (California: Sage Publications, 2008), 36.

- Transferability.
 - Measurability.**²
 - Dependability.
 - Credibility.
3. **According to WHO reference style, which one of the following is false about avoiding discriminatory languages?**
- If the name and/or sex of a correspondent are unknown, you can assume that the individual is male.**³
 - Where titles are appropriate, use parallel titles.
 - Avoid terms or expressions that are patronizing or demeaning.
 - Avoid sexist assumptions and be careful not to include hidden stereotypes.
4. **What is the advantage of using the WHO house of style?**
- It ensures consistency when writing for WHO.**⁴
 - Provides criteria for assessing the quality of manuscript.
 - It gives templet for writing different materials such as letters, report, books etc.
 - None of the above.

² Bloomberg and Volpe, 100.

³ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Malta: WHO Graphics, 2004), 59.

⁴ World Health Organization, 1.

5. **What are the primary purposes of quoting?**
- The exact wording constitutes evidence that backs up your reasons.
 - A passage states a view that you disagree with, and to be fair you want to state it exactly.
 - The quoted words are from an authority who backs up your view.
 - All of the above.**⁵
6. **Which of the following statements about plagiarism is most accurate?**
- It is possible to "copy and paste" from the internet as far as properly referenced.
 - You can use ideas or methods from a source without citing it.
 - It occurs when writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.**⁶
 - It occurs when writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.
7. **What is the purpose of the introduction in a research report?**
- Put the research in the context of another research.
 - It makes readers understand why they should read the report.
 - It gives them a framework for understanding it.
 - All are answer.**⁷

⁵ Kate L Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 8th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 49.

⁶ EUCLID, *ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Washington DC: Euclid University Press, 2015), 9.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, 70.

8. **Which one of the following is not the purposes Secondary sources?**

- To keep up with current research.
- To find other points of view.
- To find models for the research and analysis.
- None.**⁸

9. **Which of the following are false about Paraphrases?**

- You cannot just change a couple of words and rearrange the sentence structure.
- The writing style you use to express the author's ideas must be different from the style the author used
- The information that you are providing must be an accurate representation of what the author originally wrote.
- When you use a paraphrase, you must use quotation marks "....." to capture what the author has said.**⁹

10. **Which of the following is true about style guide?**

- It is a means of documenting writer's approach which enable certain elements of writing style consistent.**¹⁰
- Style guide provide guidance on punctuation and correct grammar only.
- When using style guides there is no need to be consistent in their use.
- Many creative writes encourage using style guide in writing.

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, 25.

⁹ EUCLID, 24.

¹⁰ EUCLID, 52.

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Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. California: Sage Publications, 2008.

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